

Integrating Physiological Responses Into Species Distribution Models To Forecast The Effects Of Future Ocean Warming And Oxygen Depletion On Fish Larvae Dynamics (FUTURELARVAE)

Data Management Plan

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Executive Summary

The Data Management Plan is drafted pursuant to Art.29.3 of Grant agreement no. 101038057 (FUTURELARVAE) signed between the European Commission's Research Executive Agency and ISPA CRL on 20/04/2021. The Plan's main objective is to provide open access to research data generated by the project through depositing the research outcomes in a research data repository. The Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines how the research data will be handled during the project and after it is completed. It describes what data will be collected/generated; what methodology and standards are used; whether and how this data will be shared and/or made open; and how it will be curated and preserved. The Plan describes the measures taken to enable third parties to access and disseminate (free of charge for any user) the research data. The project's DMP follows the template provided in the Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020.

1. Introduction

The Data Management Plan aims at providing open access to research outcomes generated by the project and making part of this research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR). The DMP is designed to ensure sound research data management as a key conduit leading to knowledge discovery and innovation. The document describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by FUTURELARVAE. The DMP specifies the project's participation in the Open Research Data Pilot (ORD pilot) which aims at improving and maximising access to and reuse of research data generated by H2020 projects. This DMP is a living document which will be updated over the course of the project whenever significant changes arise.

2. Data Summary

The main objective of FUTURELARVAE is to incorporate physiological and behavioural responses of fish larvae to rising temperature and O₂ depletion into species distribution models (SDMs) to mechanistically forecast the effects of climate change on the distributions of larvae (*Atherina presbyter* and *Diplodus sargus*) and the suitability of present versus future habitats to support spawning and nursery grounds. Therefore, this project accounts to qualitative and quantitative datasets collected, processed and generated along every scientific work package (WP1 to WP5). The project will make use of existing and publicly available information from databases on biodiversity, spatial agencies and from the literature.

The **data collection** consists of:

- (1) *in situ* capture of early life stages of *A. presbyter* and *D. sargus* in the wild or aquaculture research stations;
- (2) geo-referenced occurrences (GIS spatial points) of early life stages of *A. presbyter* and *D. sargus* available in open databases, such as Global Biodiversity information Facility (GBIF) and Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS), literature and research projects;
- (3) physical and biogeochemical remotely sensed data consisting of climate model projections for the present condition and future scenarios available in open databases such as .

The data collection will further be processed to generate datasets to fulfil the needs of the scientific work packages proposed in the project, specifically:

Experimental biology (WP1, WP2 and WP3)

Objective: to identify temperature- and O₂-related chronic controls in the physiological responses of *A. presbyter* and *D. sargus* larvae based on experimental biology.

Description: The *in situ* captured/transferred specimens will be used to produce an experimental dataset examining the effects of chronic thermal exposure and O₂ depletion on metabolism, behavioural traits, swimming ability, mortality, growth and biomarkers of both species in order to define optimal temperatures and O₂ levels for each physiological function.

Ecological modelling (WP4 and WP5)

Objective: to join physiological data, satellite-based oceanographic observations and SDMs to mechanistically forecast the present and future distribution (*i.e.* 2050 and 2100) of these larvae along the eastern Atlantic and western Mediterranean coasts through physiology-SDMs (computational sciences).

Description: geo-referenced occurrences of early life stages of *A. presbyter* and *D. sargus*, as well as climate model projections will be processed to produce standard species distribution models (SDMs). Thereafter, the results of experimental biology will be processed to produce response curves with coefficients that will calibrate standard-SDMs to produce physiology-SDMs through a Bayesian approach using generalized linear models (GLMs).

2.1. Types and formats of data

FUTURELARVAE is an interdisciplinary project that uses and produce several types and formats of data as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Description of the datasets

Description	Type	File	Information	Format
Species' occurrence matrices	Quantitative (continuous)	Excel	latitude and longitude	.csv
Experimental datasets	Qualitative and quantitative	Excel	physiological and behaviour tests	.excel
Climate model projections	Quantitative (continuous)	Raster	spatial maps	.GeoTIFF
Statistical Scripts	R language	Notepad	model runs and fit tests	.txt
Statistical models	Algorithms and equations	R	model results	.RDATA
Species distribution model projections	Quantitative (continuous)	Raster	spatial maps	.GeoTIFF
Scientific papers	Qualitative and quantitative	Adobe	methods and results	.pdf

2.2. Origin, re-use of existing data and expected size

Historical occurrence data of both larval species have been retrieved from published literature, database from scientific projects and open science databases (OBIS, GBIF) along the eastern Atlantic and western Mediterranean coasts (Table 2). Monthly-averaged seasonal satellite images under a GIS environment will be used as explanatory variables to model the present and future distribution of these larvae. Specifically, the mean sea surface temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), dissolved oxygen (mg m^{-3}), salinity (PSS), ocean currents (m s^{-1}), near-surface wind speed (m s^{-1}), among others, will be retrieved from open databases (Tables 3 and 4). The expected size for this dataset is approximately 10 GB.

Table 2. Number of occurrences of early life stages of *Atherina presbyter* and *Diplodus sargus* available in each database and literature. OBIS: Ocean Biogeographic Information System, GBIF: Global Biodiversity Information Facility, MARE-ISPA: Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre-University Institute, CFE: Centre for Functional Ecology.

<i>Diplodus sargus</i>			<i>Atherina presbyter</i>		
Database	Ocurrence records	year	Database	Ocurrence records	Year
CFE	2	2003-2019	CFE	2	2003-2019
Ramos et al., 2006	3	2002-2003	Ramos et al., 2015	4	2009
Torrado et al., 2021	6	-	Ramos et al., 2006	3	2002-2003
Faria et al., 2006	3	-	Rodrigues et al., 2019	3	2016-2017
Azeitero et al., 2006	3	2002-2003	Faria et al., 2006	3	-
Borges et al., 2007	9	-	Azeitero et al., 2006	3	2002-2003
Garrido et al., 2009	7	2002	Borges et al., 2007	9	-
Olivar and Sabatés, 1997	2	1992	Sabatés et al., 2003	3	1990-1991
Sabatés and Olivar, 1996	2	1992	Félix-Hackradt et al., 2013	3	2011
Sabatés, 1990	10	1983	MARE-ISPA	216	2009
Sabatés et al., 2003	5	1990-1991	OBIS	3692	1861-2019
Félix-Hackradt et al., 2013	1	2010	GBIF	1358	1993-2015
Aleman et al., 2006	1	1996	TOTAL:	5299	
d'Elbée et al., 2009	1	2000-2006			
MARE-ISPA	23	2011-2013			
OBIS	224	1987-2017			
GBIF	540	1896-2020			
TOTAL:	842				

Table 3. Description of climate model projections under annual approaches. MODIS: Moderate-resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer, WOD: World Ocean Database, ARMOR: Global Observed Ocean Physics Reprocessing, ORAP: Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis, PISCES: Global Ocean Biogeochemistry Non-assimilative Hindcast, ECMWF: European Center for Medium Range Weather Forecast, GEBCO, General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans, NASA: National Aeronautics and Space Administration, GODDARD: NASA's Goddard Space Flight Center, SSALTO: Segment Sol Multimissions d'Altimétrie, d'Orbitographie et de Localisation Précise, Duacs: Data Unification and Altimeter Combination, PODAAC: Physical Oceanography Distributed Active Archive Center. The * indicates that a variables is available for the present condition and future scenarios (2050 and 2100 RCP 8.5).

Parameter	Units	Sensor/Model	Resolution	Source of climate data	Sources of reanalyses	References
<i>(max, min, mean, range)</i>						
Sea Surface Temperature*	°C	Aqua-MODIS		ARMOR		
Sea Surface Salinity*	PSU	WOD 2009				
Current velocity*	m s ⁻¹	Multiple Sensors		ORAP		
Nitrate*	mol m ⁻³	WOD 2009				
Phosphate*	mol m ⁻³	WOD 2009	0.083°		bio-oracle.org	Assis et al., 2017
Silicate*	mol m ⁻³	WOD 2009				
Iron*	µmol m ⁻³	-		PISCES		
Dissolved molecular oxygen*	mol m ⁻³	WOD 2009				
Chlorophyll*	mg m ⁻³	Aqua-MODIS				
Phytoplankton*	µmol m ⁻³	-				
Primary productivity*	g m ⁻³ day ⁻¹	-				
Total currents	m s ⁻¹		0.25°			
Geostrophic currents	m s ⁻¹	Multiple Sensors	0.25°	GlobCurrent v2	globcurrent.ifremer.fr	Rio et al., 2014
Ekman currents	m s ⁻¹		0.25°			
Stokes drift	m s ⁻¹		0.5°			Rascle and Arduin, 2013
Wind Speed	m s ⁻¹					
Northward wind component	m s ⁻¹	Multiple Sensors	0.75°	ECMWF	apps.ecmwf.int	Dee et al., 2011
Eastward wind component	m s ⁻¹					
Bathymetry	km	Multiple Sensors	0.25°	GEBCO	gebcosetnet	GEBCO, 2020
Distance to the nearest coast	km	Generic Mapping Tools	0.01°	GODDARD	oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.org	NASA, 2009
Surface northward currents	m s ⁻¹	Multiple Sensors	0.33°	PODAAC	podaac.jpl.nasa.gov	ESR, 2009
Surface eastward currents	m s ⁻¹					
Sea surface density	kg m ⁻³			SSS/SSD L4		Droghei et al., 2016
Geostrophic northward current	m s ⁻¹	SSALTO	0.25°	ARMOR	marine.copernicus.eu	Mulet et al., 2012
Geostrophic eastward current	m s ⁻¹			ARMOR		
Sea level anomaly	m	Multiple Sensors	0.25°	ECMWF		Mertz and Legeais, 2019

Table 4. Description of climate model projections under seasonal approaches (quarterly projections) for the present-day and future scenario.

Parameters	Abbreviation	Units	Resolution	Present-day	References	Resolution	2050-2099 - RCP 8.5	References
Sea surface temperature	SST	°C	0.25°		Locarnini et al., 2018	1°		
Sea surface salinity	SSS	PSU	0.25°	NOAA's WOA 2018 Data	Zweng et al., 2018	1°		
Dissolved oxygen	DO	mol m ⁻³	0.25°		Garcia et al., 2018	1°		
Chlorophyll <i>a</i>	Chl-a	mg m ⁻³	0.25°	Copernicus-Global Ocean Biogeochemistry Analysis and Forecast	Perruche, 2019	1°	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP5)	Scott et al., 2016
Northward near-surface wind speed	NWS	m s ⁻¹	0.25°			1°		
Eastward near-surface wind speed	EWS	m s ⁻¹	0.25°	Copernicus-Global Ocean Wind L4	Bentamy, 2020	1°		
Distance to the nearest coast	DIST	km	0.01°	NASA's Goddard Space Flight Center	NASA, 2009	0.01°	NASA's Goddard Space Flight Center	NASA, 2009

2.3. Data utility

Part of the research data might be useful to researchers in the area of Environmental and Geosciences (ENV), including those in the subjects of ecology, climatology/climate change, environmental physiology, numerical analysis/scientific computing and biodiversity/conservation biology. The research data will provide a reference source also for non-specialists who are interested in marine policy.

3. FAIR Data

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The outcomes generated by FUTURELARVAE can be identifiable and located by means of a Digital Object Identifiers or by electronic references (e.g. organization websites) as they are available as open scientific information. Part of the data generated by the project, including publications (descriptive, reference and statistical metadata), will be deposited on the Zenodo platform (<https://www.zenodo.org/>), which is an EU-supported portal for big data management and extended digital library capabilities for open access and open data. More specifically, the research data and publications will be deposited on the Zenodo-curated OpenAIRE platform (<https://www.openaire.eu/>), which is the major EC-supported initiative for fostering open science in Europe. FUTURELARVAE is already registered on the OpenAIRE platform and has open access mandate for publications and research data (see https://explore.openaire.eu/search/project?projectId=corda_h2020::966943dd48995d4a4f95371fb80385fc). Each research data deposited on Zenodo/OpenAIRE is assigned a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) number which is a unique and persistent identifier. Zenodo is integrated into reporting lines for research funded by the European Commission via OpenAIRE. The data on Zenodo/OpenAIRE is preserved via reliable and well-established means, including mirroring and periodic back-ups.

The naming convention will reflect the contents of the respective research data (e.g. scripts; matrices), the project acronym (FUTURELARVAE), number of grant agreement and the year of publication. Search keywords will be provided to optimise possibilities for re-use. Search keywords will include the name of the project (FUTURELARVAE) as well as keywords relatable to the project's subject matter, such as "fish larvae ecology", "climate change", "eco-physiology", "animal behaviour", "species distribution models", "mechanistic ecological modelling". Clear version numbers will be provided, when applicable.

FUTURELARVAE is an interdisciplinary approach that joins disciplines such as experimental biology, oceanography, ecology, geophysics (GIS techniques) and computational sciences. The research data collected and processed (i.e. response and explanatory variables) for modelling purposes are already described and published as structural metadata by each author (Tables 2, 3 and 4). Results from experimental biology and those generated during the project timeline will be published as descriptive

(publications), reference (model scripts and methodologies) and statistical metadata (production of statistical data).

3.2. Making data openly accessible

We declare that because of the nature of data and the circumstances explained below, research data generated by experimental biology (WP1, WP2 and WP3) will not be openly accessible. FUTURELARVAE is a complex multidisciplinary project with multiple instances of data collection and computational effort. The different tasks described in working packages intends to feed off different scientific publication. This means that a dataset used in previously published study will be used in the next study, and so on. Given that work on the FUTURELARVAE results will extend beyond the project deadline, making the experimental datasets publicly accessible would jeopardize the achievement of the main objective of the action and the confidentiality of future publications (i.e. those submitted, under revision or as draft version). Moreover, the research data retrieved from open scientific databases for use in FUTURELARVAE is made openly available as the default on websites (Tables 3 and 4). On the other hand, the research data obtained from partner projects (e.g. species' occurrence datasets) cannot be made available (Table 2), but will be listed and referenced as supplementary information or main tables in scientific publication.

Part of the outcomes produced by FUTURELARVAE, such as experimental setup, statistical scripts and procedures will be of restricted access until these data and metadata are published as open access papers. These specific research data and open access publications will be deposited for open access or restricted access on Zenodo. The research data will be made available in .csv, .excel, .txt, .pdf formats for which free software tools can easily be downloaded. Moreover, the link to the repository will be provided on the supervisor's website (<https://amfaria.com/research/>). The project will follow the conditions, rules and regulations from the Zenodo repository with regard to accepted way of depositing the data, format and size of the research data. The MSCA-WF Fellow has already created a Zenodo account.

The Zenodo platform fully complies with the principle of accessibility of the research data. All metadata are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol (OAI-PMH). The protocol is open, free and universally implementable. The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary. Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available.

Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least. There are no restrictions on data use. No additional documentation is needed to open the research data. There is no need for a data access committee.

3.3. Making data interoperable

The data retrieved or produced by the project is fully interoperable as it is packaged in standard .csv, .excel, .txt, .pdf files. Anyone with minimum computer skills will be able to open and use these data. All of the metadata will be given in a .txt document format which is easily readable on any computer. Model runs will be presented as scripts (.txt) with R language that must be run exclusively in the open software R (R language programming). Methodological issues will be published as Open Access papers.

Zenodo follows DataCite Metadata Schema (<https://schema.datacite.org/>) which is a list of core metadata properties chosen for an accurate and consistent identification of a resource for citation and retrieval purposes, along with recommended use instructions. Hence, FUTURELARVAE metadata will be fully interoperable. No project-specific ontologies or vocabulary will be generated.

3.4. Increase data re-use

The project aims at publishing at least two open access articles under the Creative Commons licence in order to allow for a possibly widest re-use of the research output. Part of the research data from FUTURELARVAE will be deposited on Zenodo for open access or restricted access. The research data and metadata will only be freely available on Zenodo without any restrictions after the publication of the project's main results. The exact time when the data will be deposited on the platform depends on the amount of time that will be required to prepare the data. Users will be able to use the metadata without any restrictions other than the general terms and conditions for the use of data on Zenodo.

The data will remain reusable without any specified time limit under the Creative Commons licence. As per Zenodo policy, items deposited on the platform will be retained for the lifetime of the repository.

Data quality assurance is provided in line with the principles of research integrity and responsible research. Data management will be overseen by the host organization which has considerable experience with H2020 projects.

4. Allocation of resources

Costs related to open access to research data are eligible costs as part of the Horizon 2020 MSCA grant as specified in the Grant Agreement. The project will provide easy access to part of the research data using Zenodo, which is a free online repository. Depositing materials on Zenodo will not generate any costs, and all materials will be prepared and checked by the Marie Curie-WF Fellow. All publications resulting from the project will be published as open access articles in peer-reviewed journals. The costs related to open access publications (article publishing charges – APC) are eligible costs for Horizon 2020 grants under budget category Research, training and networking costs. Additionally, APC charges may be invoiced by agreement between the host institution and scientific journals. The costs for printing and preparation of the hardcopy version of the project's leaflet are also eligible under the Horizon 2020 grant. Part of the outputs generated by the project will be open for re-use and sharing without any restrictions by the end of the project. The project's main dissemination and communication objective is to popularize its findings and outcomes among the general public.

Data management will be the responsibility of the MSCA-WF Fellow and project coordinator, Dr. Ana Faria. There will be no further costs related to preservation of the data beyond the funding period.

5. Data security

All data is securely stored on two secure drives: the notebook of the Marie Curie-WF Fellow, a personal HardDrive and the host organization's Google drive. ISPA has an appointed Data Protection Office (DPO), who the ER can consult specifically for the DMP. This will ensure appropriate transfer of new methodologies, protocols, experimental approaches, data and innovation outputs, including knowledge that may require IP rights protection.

Depositing the data on Zenodo is free of charge and allows for long-term preservation and curation in compliance with the EU guidelines.

6. Ethical aspects

There is no ethical or legal issues that can have impact on data sharing. Part of the proposed research involves research on living animals and consequently will comply with the National and European legislation (European Directive 2010/63/UE) on animal

experimentation and welfare. The project will investigate the effect of chronic thermal exposure and oxygen depletion in the physiology of *Atherina presbyter* and *Diplodus sargus*, both non-endangered fish species (Least Concern of the IUCN Red List).

Fish will be housed in the fish facilities of MARE-ISPA, certified for animal housing. The number of individuals used in experiments will be kept to the minimum required for statistical power test. All the protocols are designed to minimize harm and potential for pain. All sampling and handling of fish will be performed by experienced personnel in accordance with the relevant European legislation. Euthanasia methods will comply with the European legislation and will implicate an overdose of anaesthetics. Ana M. Faria, the coordinator, is an accredited project-coordinator (FELASA, category C) by the National Authority for Animal Health (DGAV), and holds a permit to run experiments using fish, under the project “Global change effects on fish ecology, behaviour and physiology” (reference 0421/000/000/2020).

Permission for capturing fish at the field site is granted annually and will be requested to the Instituto da Conservação da Natureza e das Florestas (ICNF) – the Portuguese entity that secures the execution of policies for nature and forest conservation in compliance with Nagoya Protocol (EU 511/2014) and the most recent national legislation (DL 122/2017). Another part of the project relies to a large extent on data already available in public repositories (Open Science), and from previous and ongoing projects, and no further ethical issues are foreseen. FUTURELARVAE does not involve research into human embryos/fetuses or tissue nor have any 'Dual' uses or environmental risks.

7. Other issues

The project does not make use of other national / funder / sectorial / departmental procedures for data management.

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